

FABRICATION of GO-KART DRIVEN by ELECTRIC POWER SOURCE

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Abstract— The project presents the design and construction methodology for a low-cost solar-powered go-kart aimed at daily commuters. Focusing on eco-friendly transportation, the project utilizes photovoltaic cells to convert solar energy into electrical power. A microcontroller-based charge controller efficiently manages the flow of energy to a battery pack, ensuring optimal storage and utilization. The objective is to provide a reliable and economical means of short-distance commuting, powered by renewable solar energy. Through an array of solar panels, energy is harvested and stored in the battery pack for later use. The stored energy is then directed to a DC motor, propelling the go-kart. The integration of solar power reduces environmental impact and showcases the potential of clean energy in transportation. Collaboration with automotive and mechanical engineering students enhances the design process with diverse expertise. Analysing existing literature and papers on solar go-karts informs the project's methodology and design decisions. Documenting progress and insights contributes to the collective knowledge in eco-friendly transportation technology.

Keywords— Battery-powered go-kart, electric vehicle, renewable energy, battery technology, vehicle design.

I. INTRODUCTION.

A. Overview of Battery-Powered Go-Kart

Battery-powered go-karts represent a sustainable evolution in motorsport, offering a clean alternative to conventional gasoline models. This transition responds to urgent environmental imperatives, aiming to reduce emissions and conserve finite fossil fuel resources [1]. With advancements in battery technology, these vehicles deliver comparable performance while minimizing noise pollution and operating costs [3]. Moreover, batterypowered go-karts provide an eco-friendly platform for racing enthusiasts, aligning with global efforts towards a greener automotive future.

The integration of battery technology in go-karts not only enhances performance but also promotes sustainable racing practices [2]. By embracing electric propulsion, drivers can enjoy the thrill of motorsport while minimizing their environmental footprint [4]. This shift underscores a broader trend towards cleaner transportation solutions, signaling a transformative step towards sustainable and responsible approach to racing.

Fig 1: 3-D rendered Go-Kart Image [4] B. Overview of the Project

The project's objective is to design, develop, and implement a high-performance electric go-kart powered by rechargeable batteries. This project seeks to showcase the feasibility and advantages of electric propulsion in recreational racing, emphasizing sustainability, efficiency, and innovation in the karting industry.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Naveen Kumar, Sumith Mishra, Siddharth Mishra, et al., [1]. Present a holistic methodology for crafting a secure, robust, and high-performing go-kart, with meticulous attention to the chassis, powertrain, braking, and steering mechanisms. Their work underscores the utilization of CAD software for intricate design processes and FEA for rigorous analysis, while prioritizing safety, endurance, ergonomics, and efficiency. Noteworthy is the incorporation of a hybrid powertrain and the unwavering focus on safety via structural design and analysis, exemplifying an exhaustive engineering endeavor.

Prof. Ambepasad Kushwaha, et al.,[2] Aim to design a cost-effective electric go-kart to reduce reliance on fossil fuels, involving calculations for speed, braking, steering, and battery selection, alongside deformation and stress analysis, concluding with successful budget-conscious fabrication.

Aklesh Kumar Yadav, et al.,[3] Present a thorough examination of an electric go-kart's design and analysis, prioritizing chassis, steering, brakes, and battery selection. Employing AISI 4130 for the chassis material, Solidworks2018 for modeling, and finite element analysis, they achieve a factor of safety of 15 and maximum stress of 337.84 MPa. Additionally, the paper optimizes battery selection considering performance, cost, and energy efficiency, showcasing a comprehensive approach to electric vehicle engineering.

Mohammed Al-Garni, et al.,[4] Elucidate the importance of go-karts as lightweight, racing-centric vehicles in their literature review, examining previous studies and comparative analyses on weight reduction strategies. In the system design section, they delineate essential constraints including weight, compactness, ergonomics, and environmental factors, stressing the necessity of a well-defined design methodology for streamlined project implementation.

Morisho Penesenga Jenny, et al.,[5] Meticulously detail the design considerations and specifications for a go-kart, with a focus on the chassis, steering system, axle selection for traction, powertrain, motor specifications, chain and gear mechanism, battery selection, speed controller, and braking system. The chassis is engineered to provide secure enclosure for the vehicle and driver, utilizing materials such as angle irons and AISI 1020 steel to ensure durability and safety. Each component is thoroughly discussed, highlighting the comprehensive approach taken in designing a high-performance and reliable go-kart.

Shaik Imam Saheb, et al.,[6] Present a detailed account of the design and engineering process for a Go Kart intended for a student karting championship, with paramount emphasis on safety, functionality, and costeffectiveness. Leveraging CAD software and ANSYS for analysis, the team meticulously selected IS1161 seamless tube for the chassis, while designing components based on market availability and adherence to safe engineering practices. This approach underscores the team's commitment to delivering a competitive and reliable karting solution within stringent safety and budgetary constraints.

Ashish Porwal, et al.,[7] Present a comprehensive report detailing the design and fabrication of an electric go-kart, with a keen emphasis on safety, performance, and cost-effectiveness. The report highlights the utilization of CAD software for meticulous modeling, AISI 4130 for the roll cage to ensure robust safety measures, and the integration of a BLDC motor powered by a lithium-ion battery for enhanced performance and efficiency. This holistic approach underscores the team's commitment to delivering a reliable and sustainable electric go-kart solution suitable for various racing applications.

Kiran Lal, et al.,[8] Showcase a comprehensive approach to the design, analysis, and fabrication of a go-kart, with a primary focus on affordability and safety. The paper delves into the utilization of AISI 1080 mild/low carbon steel for the frame, a steering system adhering to Ackermann design principles, and a disc brake setup for efficient braking.

Mainak Mitra, et al.,[9] Meticulously outline the design and analysis of a go-kart in their article, encompassing crucial aspects such as frame material selection, safety analysis, steering system design, power transmission shaft considerations, powertrain optimization, wheel specifications, and the implementation of an innovative regenerative braking system. The article places significant emphasis on adhering to stringent safety standards while striving for efficiency and performance optimization to create a competitive go-kart design that excels in both racing prowess and technological innovation.

Mohan Ramesh Choudhary, et al.,[10] Employ CREO Parametric 2.0 and ANSYS Workbench 14.0 to design and analyze an electric kart chassis tailored to accommodate 95% of male and female individuals in India. Constructed from AISI 1018 for its availability and cost-effectiveness, the chassis withstands front, rear, and side impacts at speeds up to 90 km/h, exhibiting stress levels below the material's ultimate tensile stress, ensuring safety and suitability for high-performance karting.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Hardware Components:

Electric Motor: Electric motor provides high torque for quick acceleration and good top speeds. They're powered by rechargeable batteries

Brush Controller: A brush controller typically refers to a device or component used to control the behavior and properties of a brush in digital art software.

Chain Drive: The chain drive consists of a sprocket attached to the motor shaft and another sprocket mounted on the rear axle. When the motor turns, it rotates the first sprocket, which in turn rotates the second sprocket, propelling the go-kart forward.

Table 1: Component Specifications

COMPONENT	FUNCTION	SPECIFICATION
Electric Motor	Used for propulsion	DC Motor
Battery	To store electric charges	12v Battery
Brush Controller	Used to control the behaviour of the brushes	Range – 250watt
Chain Drive	Used to drive the power to the wheels	Module – 2.75mm

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Achievements in Flexibility and Functionality

The electric battery-operated go-kart displayed impressive performance during testing, showcasing swift acceleration and achieving desired top speeds efficiently. These initial findings highlight the potential of electric propulsion systems in delivering dynamic driving experiences. The seamless integration of electric motors and controllers ensured smooth power delivery, contributing to the go-kart's responsive handling and agility on the track.

2. Battery efficiency

An essential aspect of the discussion revolves around battery efficiency and endurance under various conditions. Analysis of energy consumption patterns and battery discharge rates provided insights into the go-kart's endurance capabilities. Optimizing these factors is crucial for extending the vehicle's range and operational lifespan, particularly for competitive racing scenarios or prolonged recreational use.

3. Safety and Performance

Safety considerations were paramount, emphasizing the implementation of robust safety features to mitigate potential risks associated with high-speed electric vehicles. Measures such as roll cages, seat belts, and emergency kill switches were vital for ensuring driver safety during operation. Further research into intelligent safety systems could offer enhancements in accident prevention and driver protection, fostering wider acceptance of electric gokarts in diverse environments.

4. Future scope and improvements

In conclusion, the results and discussions highlight the promising future of electric battery-operated go-karts, offering exhilarating performance while prioritizing efficiency and safety. Ongoing efforts in battery optimization, safety feature integration, and performance refinement will be crucial for advancing electric go-kart technology and promoting its widespread adoption in recreational and competitive driving arenas.

Fig 2: Chassis Construction of our working model

V. CONCLUSIONS

In concluding the project "Fabrication of Go Kart Using Electric Power Source," the integration of electric power sources, whether fully electric or hybrid, has showcased significant advancements in performance and efficiency, surpassing conventional combustion engines in acceleration, top speed, and overall drivability. This transition underscores a commitment to sustainable transportation, reducing emissions and promoting energy conservation, while also highlighting the feasibility and benefits of electrification in the automotive sector. Leveraging innovative technologies such as advanced battery management systems and regenerative braking, this project exemplifies the potential for electric vehicle innovation, with future prospects including optimizing hybrid power systems, enhancing vehicle dynamics, and integrating smart technologies to further drive sustainable change and propel the automotive industry towards a greener, more efficient future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Gratitude to Prof. Shreyas P S, Dr. Niranjana Hiremath, Dr. Mahesh L, and Dr. K S Narayanaswamy for guidance and support. Special thanks to Dr. P Shyama Raju for the educational opportunity. Appreciation to family, friends, and the almighty for their encouragement and strength throughout the project.

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